

SECTION OF CHEMICAL SCIENCES

CARBOXY DERIVATIVES OF PYRUVIC ACID AS SYNTHONS FOR TETRAHYDROPYRIMIDINES

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Abstract

For the first time, methods for the synthesis of new tetrahydropyrimidinones and tetrahydropyrimidinethiones using carboxy derivatives of pyruvic acid as the methylene carbonyl component and the DMF/TMSCl system were developed and optimized. General methods for the synthesis of tetrahydropyrimidinones and tetrahydropyrimidinethiones derivatives based on unsubstituted, monosubstituted and disubstituted ureas and thioureas have been developed.

Keywords: carboxy derivatives of pyruvic acid, tetrahydropyrimidinones, tetrahydropyrimidinethiones, unsubstituted, monosubstituted and disubstituted ureas and thioureas, DMF/TMSCl system.

Introduction.

Use of different variations of reagents in synthesis

tetrahydropyrimidines

1. Acetoacetic acid esters and β -diketones

Figure 1. Synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2-(1H)-ones of the general formula (1).

This reaction is currently undergoing a new stage of development. It was found that 6-methyl-4-phenyl-2-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine ethyl carboxylate is formed during the condensation of acetoacetic ester with urea and benzaldehyde. An identical product can be obtained: a) by the interaction of benzaldehyde with β -carbamidocrotonic ester, b) by the reaction of benzylidene diureide with acetoacetic ester, c) by condensation of α -benzalacetoacetate with urea. These counter-syntheses unambiguously proved the structure of 6-methyl-4-phenyl-2-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine ethyl carboxylate. The next article devoted to this cyclocondensation was published only in 1929 [2]. In the early 1930s, attention was paid to this reaction by Folkes, Hartwood, and Johnson [3]. They proposed a modified method of its implementation, thanks to

At the end of the 19th century, the synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2-(1H)-ones of the general formula (1) was carried out by the method of condensation of aromatic aldehyde, urea and acetoacetic ester [1].

which it was possible to expand the range of reagents and increase product yields.

In the following years, until the end of the 30s, only about a dozen publications on this topic were published. With the development of pharmaceutical chemistry, interest in tetrahydropyrimidine derivatives began to grow. Reviews were published [4-6]. The number of articles since the beginning of the 70s has reached over a hundred.

The fact that the reaction is three-component makes it possible to vary the structure of its products. So as a methylene carbonyl component derivatives of β -ketoacetic acids, β -diketones, α -nitro-, α -aryl- and some α -heteryl ketones and aldehydes were used. Aldehydes are aromatic and

heteroaromatic, some aliphatic. Substituted and unsubstituted ureas, thioureas, and guanidines were introduced into the reaction.

The participation of β -keto acid esters and β -diketones is the most widespread modification of the cyclocondensation reaction.

X = O, S; R = Ar, Alk

Figure 2. Cyclocondensation involving esters of β -keto acids and β -diketones

In this case, when R = Me, Et, Ph, OMe, OEt, the reaction has high yields even when it is carried out under standard conditions (HCl/EtOH) and requires special conditions only in the presence of electron-withdrawing substituents in the aldehyde component or when thioureas participate in the reaction. In addition

to condensation products with arylaldehydes, products based on heterocyclic aldehydes were obtained (the best yield for 2-thiophencarbaldehyde was 52%, the lowest yield for 8-quinolinecarbaldehyde was 28.6%) [7]:

Figure 3. Products based on heterocyclic aldehydes

For the reaction with aliphatic aldehydes, cyclocondensation products were obtained with significantly lower yields than for aryl and heterarylaldehydes [8]:

Figure 4. Products based on aliphatic aldehydes

For this reason, modified methods were developed. Two modifications of the cyclocondensation reaction are widespread: using "hidden carbonyl equivalents" and Etwell's modification [9].

The idea of using substances in the reaction, which in the reaction medium would give an aldehyde, which

later participates in condensation, was implemented in the work [43, 44], where 2-substituted 1,3-oxazinans were used:

Figure 5. Using substances in the reaction, which in the reaction medium would give an aldehyde

To introduce guanidines into the reaction, as well as to obtain O- or S-alkylated 1,4-dihydropyrimidines, it is convenient to use the modification proposed by Etwell [9]. In this method, the previously obtained benzylidene- β -ketoester adds guanidine according to Michael, followed by cyclization to 1,4-dihydropyrimidine. It is proposed to use the method for electron-deficient aldehydes, cyclohexylcarbaldehyde and some others.

Instead of HCl, acetic or p-toluenesulfonic acid is used as a catalyst [10]. The best results were obtained in the presence of boron trifluoride [45], polyphosphoric ether [11], lanthanide compounds LaCl₃ [12], Yb(OTf)₃ [13], lithium bromide [14], under conditions of microwave irradiation [15] and the so-called "solvent-free" reaction conditions (using a mixture of

acidic or basic Yb(III)-modified polymers and a solid acid catalyst [16]) in the presence of ionic liquids, such as 1-n-butyl-3-methylimidazole tetrafluoroborate or its hexafluorophosphate [17].

Choosing an effective catalyst allows you to significantly increase yields. So, for example, for 2-bromo-4-nitrobenzaldehyde, the yield according to the standard method is close to 20%. The use of ytterbium triflate allows to increase it to 52% [13].

2. α -Aryl- and α -heterylcarbonyl compounds in the cyclocondensation reaction.

The possibility of using α -arylcarbonyl compounds in cyclocondensations was shown in an early work [21] using the example of acetophenone and phenylacetaldehyde:

Figure 6. The possibility of using α -arylcarbonyl compounds in cyclocondensations

Variation of aromatic substituents logically led to the use of α -heteryl carbonyl compounds as methylene carbonyl components. Thus, in [22] the reaction of 2-

phenacylbenzothiazole with aldehydes and urea (thiourea) was studied:

Figure 7. The reaction of 2-phenacylbenzothiazole with aldehydes and urea (thiourea)

Under the conditions of catalysis by alcoholic HCl, a mixture of products was obtained, which could not be separated. After optimizing the reaction conditions, the solvent, temperature, and ratio of reagents were selected. Cyclocondensation was carried out in acetic acid at 50°C. The molar ratio of aldehyde, phenacylbenzothiazole, and urea was 1:1.1:3. In this way, a yield of 72-97% was achieved.

The resulting cyclocondensation products are subjected to further functionalization. Thus, in [23], a con-

venient method for the synthesis of N(3)-ethoxycarbonyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-(1H)-2-one was developed, which consists in its acylation with a mixture of thionyl chloride and carboxylic acid.

In the thionyl chloride-carboxylic acid system (1:1 mol.), sufficient solubility of the starting compound is achieved due to an excess of acid. The optimal ratio for acylation of the starting substance, acid and thionyl chloride is 1:10:10 (mol). Under these conditions, it was possible to obtain N(3)-acyl derivatives with yields of 47-70%.

Figure 8. Use of thionyl chloride

Another example of successful N-acylation is the synthesis of 3-(2-chloroacetyl)-6-methyl-2-oxo-4-phenyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidin-5-carboxylate by the

action of chloroacetic anhydride on 3,4-tetrahydro-2H-pyrimidin-2-one. When interacting with thiourea in ethanol, an S-substituted derivative of isothiourea is formed:

Figure 9. Action of chloroacetic anhydride on 3,4-tetrahydro-2H-pyrimidin-2-one.

The use of functionalized acetophenones [21]:

A = NO₂, Cl, OMe, OPh, SPh, NHC(O)CH₃

Figure 10. The use of functionalized acetophenones

In [24, 25] it was proposed to use nitroacetone. The reaction was carried out under standard conditions

(HCl/EtOH). The product was obtained with a yield of 91%:

R = CH₃, Ph; X = O, S

Figure 11. Use of nitroacetone

A significant expansion of the spectrum of methylene components and the selection of new reaction conditions led to improved yields for low-activity aldehydes. At the same time, the circle of ureas is practically limited only to unsubstituted urea and thiourea.

Physiological activity of condensation products

Tetrahydropyrimidines (THP) have a wide spectrum of physiological activity. In the 1930s, their simplest representatives, for example (2a), were patented as insecticides [33]. Later, the effective antiviral drug nitracin (3a) was discovered [34]. Tetrahydropyrimidines manifest themselves as antitumor agents [35, 36].

Figure 12. Physiologically active THP

Compounds of type (4a) have antipyretic properties and are anticoagulants [37].

However, THPs are most interesting as antihypertensive agents, for example, analogues of nifedipine

(6a) and (7a) [38, 39]. Particularly active in this area are the disputes substituted by the provision of N-3: (8a) and (9a) [40].

Figure 13. Analogues of nifedipine (6a), (7a), (8a), (9a)

The ability of dihydropyrimidines to block calcium ion channels is described. 1,4-Dihydropyrimidines (nifedipine, nitrendipine, nimodipine, amlodipine, lacidipine, felodipine, nicardipine, isradipine, etc.) are antagonists of L-type calcium antagonists.

The action of these drugs is focused on lowering blood pressure. Due to this, some of them act as sedatives and are medicines for optic nerve dysfunction.

Known derivatives of the 4-oxopyrimidine series containing heterocyclic substituents, namely: imidazole, pyridine, thiazole, which have antihistaminic activity.

Derivatives of 4(3H)-pyrimidines have a tranquilizing effect. Oxo-1,4-dihydropyrimidine salts have antidepressant and tranquilizing effects.

The synthesis of oxo-1,4-dihydropyrimidine derivatives, which have immunotropic activity, is described [41,42].

Figure 14. Derivatives of 4(3H)-pyrimidines have a tranquilizing effect.

Figure 15. Synthesis of 6-oxo-1,4-dihydropyrimidine derivatives

The conducted studies show that the described compounds have a pronounced antihistamine effect, which is two or more times greater than the activity of diazolin, while being practically non-toxic.

Materials and methods.

Chromatograms and LC/MS spectra were obtained on an "Agilent 1100 Series" instrument equipped with an "Agilent LC/MSD SL" detector.

¹H NMR spectra (400 MHz and 500 MHz) were recorded on Varian Mercury-400 and Bruker Avance DRX 500 NMR spectrometers with TMS as an internal standard.

All reagents were obtained from commercially available sources (Aldrich, Fluka) and were used without further purification. DMF was freshly distilled and dried by a standard method. Control of the amount of water in the solvents (<0.05%) was performed by the Fisher method using a Mettler Toledo DL31 KF Titrator. Melting points were measured on a Buchi appa-

atus. Before determining the melting temperature, performing elemental analysis and spectral studies, all product samples were dried for 3-5 hours in a vacuum of 12-15 mm. at 80-100°C.

General method of synthesis of derivatives of tetrahydropyrimidinones and tetrahydropyrimidinethiones from unsubstituted ureas and thioureas.

To a solution of 0.022 mmol of urea or thiourea in 20 ml of DMF, add 0.01 mmol of aldehyde and 0.01 mmol of diketone and stir until dissolved. Then add 15 ml (~0.12 mmol) of Me₃SiCl and quickly cover with a stopper. The flask with the reaction mixture is left for 48 hours at room temperature. After completion of the reaction (a sign is the delamination of the reaction mass), the reaction mass is poured with stirring into 50-60 ml of ice water. The deposited precipitate is filtered, washed with water and 2-3 times with methanol in portions of 10 ml. The filtered sediment is dried in air. Recrystallized from methanol. The yields of target products are 80-86%.

General method of synthesis of tetrahydropyrimidinone and tetrahydropyrimidinethione derivatives from monosubstituted ureas and thioureas.

To a solution of 0.022 mmol of urea or thiourea in 20 ml of DMF, add 0.01 mmol of aldehyde and 0.01 mmol of diketone and stir until dissolved. Then 15 ml (~0.12 mmol) of Me₃SiCl is added and immediately closed with a cap. The reactor with the reaction mixture is left for 4 days at room temperature. After completion of the reaction (a sign is the delamination of the reaction mass), the reaction mass is poured with stirring into 50-60 ml of ice water. The deposited precipitate is filtered, washed with water and 2-3 times with methanol in portions of 10 ml. The filtered sediment is dried in air. Recrystallized from ethanol. The yields of target products are 82-90%.

General method of synthesis of tetrahydropyrimidinone and tetrahydropyrimidinethione derivatives from disubstituted ureas and thioureas.

13a: R = Ph
13b: R = Cl-Ph
13c: R = thiophen-2-yl
13d: R = furan-2-yl
13e: R = cyclopropyl

14a: X = O, R₁ = R₂ = H
14b: X = O, R₁ = H, R₂ = Me
14c: X = O, R₁ = R₂ = Me

14d: X = S, R₁ = R₂ = H
14e: X = S, R₁ = H, R₂ = Me
14f: X = S, R₁ = H, R₂ = Ph

Figure 16. Use of model compounds

The synthesis of carboxy derivatives of pyruvic acid was carried out according to Claisen using ketones and diethyl oxalate in the presence of sodium ethylate:

Figure 17. The synthesis of carboxy derivatives of pyruvic acid

A number of CDPA were synthesized for further use in the heterocyclization reaction: 2,4-Dioxo-4-phenyl-ethyl-butanoate (13a), 4-(4-Chlorophenyl)-2,4-dioxo-ethyl-butanoate (13b), 2,4-Dioxo-4-(thiophen-2-yl)-methylbutanoate (13c), 2,4-Dioxo-4-(furan-2-yl)-methylbutanoate (13d), 2,4-Dioxo-4-cyclopropyl-methylbutanoate (13e).

First, unsubstituted ureas (14a) and thioureas (14d) were introduced into the reaction. The reagents were taken in the following ratio: urea (thiourea) : aldehyde : CDPA : Me₃SiCl = 1 : 1 : 1 : 4. The reaction took place for 24-48 hours at room temperature:

Figure 18. unsubstituted ureas (14a) and thioureas (14d) were introduced into the reaction.

As a result, derivatives (15) were obtained.

The following experiments were carried out using substituted ureas and thioureas, which reacted well with β -diketones. When switching to monosubstituted ureas

and thioureas, the dependence of the behavior of CDPA (13a-d) on which urea entered the reaction was observed.

In the case of X = O (14b), the formation of analogues of compounds (16) was observed. And when X

= S (14e, 14g) – the formation of compounds of type (17), in which the hydroxy group remains in position 4:

Figure 19. The formation of compounds (16) or (17) depending on the nature of X

The following reaction mechanism in the presence of Me_3SiCl was proposed:

Figure 20. reaction mechanism in the presence of Me_3SiCl

At the first stage, an iminium intermediate (3a) is formed in the protonated form (3b). The next stage – addition of silylated 2,4-dioxo-ethylpentanoate (3c) to imine (3a) leads to the final 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2-(1H)-ones or -thiones. The formation of products with a substituent precisely in position 1 was proven by means of NOE.

As a result, the following substances were obtained: 5-benzoyl-1,3-dimethyl-2-oxo-6-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyrimidine-4-ethylcarboxylate (2a), 5-benzoyl-3-methyl-2-oxo-6-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyrimidine-4-ethylcarboxylate (2b), 5-benzoyl-4-hydroxy-3-methyl-6-phenyl-2-thiooxo-hexahydropyrimidine-4-ethylcarboxylate (2c), 5-benzoyl-2-oxo-6-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyrimidine-4-ethylcarboxylate (2d), 5-benzoyl-6-phenyl-2-thiooxo-tetrahydropyrimidine-4-ethylcarboxylate (2e), 5-(4-chlorobenzoyl)-6-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-oxo-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyrimidine-4-ethylcarboxylate (2f), 5-(4-chlorobenzoyl)-6-(4-chlorophenyl)-4-hydroxy-3-methyl-2-thiooxo-hexahydropyrimidine-4-ethylcarboxylate (2g), 5-(4-chlorobenzoyl)-6-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-methyl-2-oxo-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyrimidine-4-ethylcarboxylate (2h), 4-hydroxy-3-methyl-6-phenyl-5-(thiophene-2-car-

bonyl)-2-thiooxo-hexahydropyrimidine-4-ethylcarboxylate (2i), 3-methyl-2-oxo-6-phenyl-5-(thiophene-2-carbonyl)-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyrimidine-4-ethylcarboxylate (2j), 5-(furan-2-carbonyl)-3-methyl-2-thiooxo-6-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyrimidine-4-ethylcarboxylate (2k), 5-(furan-2-carbonyl)-3-methyl-2-oxo-6-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyrimidine-4-ethylcarboxylate (2l), 5-(cyclopropanecarbonyl)-4-hydroxy-3-methyl-6-phenyl-2-thiooxo-hexahydropyrimidine-4-ethylcarboxylate (2m), 5-(cyclopropanecarbonyl)-3-methyl-2-oxo-6-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyrimidine-4-ethylcarboxylate (2n), 5-(cyclopropanecarbonyl)-1,3-dimethyl-2-oxo-6-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyrimidine-4-ethylcarboxylate (2o), 5-benzoyl-4-hydroxy-3,6-diphenyl-2-thiooxo-hexahydropyrimidine-4-ethylcarboxylate (2p).

The analysis of ^1H NMR spectra showed that in the case of monosubstituted thioureas, the water molecule was not cleaved and the hydroxy group remained in position 4. No such effect was observed when monosubstituted ureas were used. The structure of 5-benzoyl-4-hydroxy-3-methyl-6-phenyl-2-thiooxo-hexahydropyrimidine-4-ethylcarboxylate (2c) was reliably proved by ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, DMSO-d_6):

Figure 21. ^1H NMR spectrum 5-Benzoyl-4-hydroxy-3-methyl-6,2-thiooxo-hexahydropyrimidine-4-ethylcarboxylate (2c)

Evidence of the presence of a hydroxy group in compound (2c) is the presence of corresponding characteristic signals. Doublets of hydrogen atoms are observed at 4.63 ppm. (H in position 5) and 4.95 ppm. (H in position 6). This indicates the absence of a double bond in the pyrimidine cycle.

In addition, a singlet of the hydrogen atom of the OH group is observed in the spectrum at 7.37 ppm. After washing D_2O , this signal disappears. The hydrogen atom of the NH group was determined by the characteristic singlet at 8.80 ppm.

The given spectrum can be compared with the spectrum.

Figure 22. 5-Benzoyl-3-methyl-2-oxo-6-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyrimidine-4-ethylcarboxylate (2b)

A characteristic signal in the spectrum is a doublet at 5.30 ppm. It can only be the H atom in C 6. In posi-

tion 4, the signal of the H atom is absent, which indicates a double bond between carbon atoms 4 and 5. The hydrogen atom of the OH group is also absent.

Figure 23. ^1H NMR spectrum 5-Benzoyl-3-methyl-2-oxo-6-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyrimidine-4-ethylcarboxylate (2b)

Conclusions.

1. A method for the synthesis of new tetrahydropyrimidinones and tetrahydropyrimidinethiones using carboxy derivatives of pyruvic acid as a methylene carbonyl component was developed and optimized.

2. It is possible to use the developed methodology for the synthesis of combinatorial libraries of compounds that are promising physiologically active substances.

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